

Synthesis of Potential Antiradiation Agents. Part III. Some N-Alkyl-2 thiono-4-oxo-and 2, 4-Dithiono-1, 3-thiazane Derivatives

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Some N-substituted 2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane derivatives and the corresponding 2,4-dithiono-1,3-thiazanes have been synthesised as potential antiradiation agents. N-substituted dithiocarbamic acids on treatment with substituted acrylic acids followed by cyclisation gave N-alkylated 2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane derivatives. These 2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazanes on refluxing with phosphorus pentasulphide in xylene resulted in the corresponding 2,4-dithiono-1,3-thiazanes. Synthesis of some of the products by alternate routes has been carried out and spectral evidence in support of their structures has been discussed.

In continuation of our work on 1,3-thiazane derivatives as potential antiradiation agents¹ we have now synthesised a number of N-alkylated-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazanes and N-alkylated-2,4-dithiono-1,3-thiazanes.

Acrylic acid was treated with methyldithiocarbamic acid and the resulting product cyclised by treatment with a mixture of acetic anhydride and H_2SO_4 to give a yellow solid, crystallisable from benzene. The UV absorption spectrum of this product showed absorption maxima at 310 and 267 $m\mu$ similar to that reported by Garraway² for 3-alkyl-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazanes. The IR spectrum showed characteristic strong absorption at 1700 cm^{-1} for $C=O$ and at 1455 cm^{-1} for thiouride grouping. The product was therefore assigned the structure 3-methyl-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane (I). Likewise, 3,6-dimethyl-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane (II) and 3,5-dimethyl-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane (III) were prepared by reacting methyldithiocarbamic acid with crotonic acid and methacrylic acid respectively, followed by cyclisation.

Compounds (I, II, III) were also prepared alternatively by the treatment of β -bromopropionic acid, β -bromobutyric acid and methyl β -bromoisobutyrate respectively with methyldithiocarbamic acid, followed by the cyclisation of the resulting intermediate products using acetic anhydride and H_2SO_4 . These products were found to be identical with compounds prepared by the earlier route on comparison of m.p., mixed m.p., TLC, UV and IR spectra.

The 3-allyl-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane derivatives (IV, V, VI) were likewise prepared from allyldithiocarbamic acid and acrylic acid, crotonic acid and methacrylic acid respectively. The condensation products on cyclisation, gave liquid products yellow in colour which were purified by distillation under vacuum.

1. V. R. Mamdapur, A. S. U. Choughuley and M. S. Chadha, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, '9'6, **43**, 37.
2. J. L. Garraway, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 4032.

The UV spectra of IV, V and VI showed absorption maxima at 313 and 267 $m\mu$ similar to those for the N-methyl-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazanes. The IR spectra showed strong bands at 1705 cm^{-1} for C = O, 1425 cm^{-1} for thiouride grouping and 1650, 990-980 and 920-905 cm^{-1} for terminal vinyl grouping.

Some 2,4-dithiono-1,3-thiazane derivatives were also synthesised as described below with the hope that an additional thio function might lead to better radioprotective activity. 2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane on treatment with P_2S_5 in xylene under reflux gave a product crystallisable from benzene. On the basis of elemental analysis and infrared spectrum wherein the carbonyl peak in the region 1690-1710 cm^{-1} was absent and an additional peak at 1205 cm^{-1} for C = S had appeared, the compound was assigned the structure, 2,4-dithiono-1,3-thiazane (VII)³. The UV absorption at 344 and 317 $m\mu$ may be attributed to the formation of the new chromophoric group wherein C = S has replaced C = O. The various 2,4-dithiono-1,3-thiazanes (VII-XII) were prepared in an analogous way.

NMR spectra of all the compounds discussed above were in accord with the assigned structures. 3-Methyl-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazanes showed singlet in the region δ 3.65-3.75 for N-CH₃ group. C-CH₃ appeared as doublet in the region δ 1.4-1.5 (J = 6-7 cps). Complex multiplet in the region δ 2.5-4.0 integrating for 3 protons (4 protons in the unsubstituted compounds) was due to overlapping signals of methylene and methine in 5 and 6 positions.

In case of 3-allyl-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazanes⁴ multiplet in the region δ 5.0-6.0 integrating for 5 protons was attributed to allyl group.

The 2,4-dithiono-1,3-thiazanes showed similar signals while N-CH₃ singlet appeared at lower field (δ 4.2).

EXPERIMENTAL

NMR spectra : In $CDCl_3$, with TMS as internal standard, values in δ ; Varian A-60-A NMR spectrometer. UV spectra : In CH_3OH ; Zeiss Recording Spectrophotometer RPK 20A. IR spectra : Solid samples as KBr pallets and liquids as films; Perkin Elmer Infracord Spectrophotometer 137 B.

Preparation of 2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazanes : Sodium methylthiocarbamate : To an ice cold solution of sodium hydroxide (40 g., 1 mole) in alcohol (250 ml.) methylamine gas was passed till the increase in weight was 30 to 35 g. To this solution, carbon disulphide (60 ml., 1 mole) in ether (300 ml.) was added portionwise with stirring at 0°. The mixture was kept at 0° for 3 hr. and left overnight at room temperature, when a crystalline solid separated out. This was filtered and washed with ether. The product was obtained in 60-70 % yield.

3-Methyl-2-thiono-4-oxo-1,3-thiazane : Method (A) : Sodium methylthiocarbamate (16 g.) was dissolved in water (30 ml.), cooled to 0° and acidified with hydrochloric acid to pH 3. To this, alcoholic solution of acrylic acid (8 g.) was added with stirring and then the reaction mixture was kept at 10-15° for four days. Alcohol was removed by distillation

3. O. V. Vladimirskaia, *Farmatsevt. Zh. (Kiev)*, 1965, 20, 3.

4. E. Campaigne and P. K. Nargund, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, 7, 132.